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ModelSEN Socio-epistemic networks: Modelling Historical Knowledge Processes

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1. The Workshop

In April 2022, scholars from a variety of different disciplines and training met in Berlin for a workshop on historical networks organized by ModelSEN¹. This workshop brought together scholars, who have a joint interest in approaches drawn from multi-layer network analysis to investigate historical processes that involve layers of different kinds and include both social and epistemic components. This paper summarizes the outcomes and is intended to serve as a starting point for further discussions and the strengthening of a community in Historical Network Research (HNR).

2. The Audience of the White Paper

The interest of the workshop participants primarily concerns either the application of network approaches to the investigation of historical processes or the development of such methods, approaches, and tools to address historical questions. The exchanges during the workshop clearly showed that discussions in the field of HNR would largely benefit from the inclusion of a larger group of historians which either are already applying methods of HNR or using networks qualitatively as an analytic instrument. Also, an intensified cooperation with scholars active in the field of Social Network Analysis (SNA), network science, complex systems, and computer science is needed to further promote methodological innovation and statistical rigor in HNR. To summarize, the group we are targeting with this white paper are scholars interested in using and refining methods from network research as heuristic tools in the hermeneutic circle.

3. Who We Are

The participants' historical projects² include various areas of research in distinct historical periods. One major group of research projects relates to the historical investigations of the Republic of Letters and the related correspondence network in the early modern period (Heuvel and Miert 2013, Hyvönen and Leskinen 2018, Rossini 2022, Vugt and Miert 2022). An analysis of correspondence networks also characterizes the research based on the exchange of letters in the early romanticism period (Deicke 2023). The second largest group of historical projects is interested in a network perspective on 20th century history of economics, using a variety of different sources, most prominently publications and journals (Baccini and Petrovich 2017, Doehne and

¹<https://modelsen.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de>.

²See the project bibliography in Section 9 for details about the researchers' projects.

Herfeld 2019), but also event rosters, attendance records, institutional affiliations, informal collaboration reports and patterns, and researcher mobility patterns over time. Other historical projects are less closely related thematically, but still share similarities in terms of research questions and approaches (see below). These include: The history of modern physics and astronomy (Lalli 2018), the history of analytic philosophy (Petrovich 2021), the history of medicine (Fangerau and Hentschel 2018), the history of the scientific system of cosmological knowledge (Büttner and Valleriani 2020), and the history of data sharing (Turchetti, Lalli, and Kinyanjuy 2022).

Beyond the historical projects that the ModelSEN project aims to bring into constructive dialogue, some scholars are additionally involved at different method-oriented levels (Düring 2020, Hyvönen and Leskinen 2018, Olbrich 2022). One of these concerns the development of ontologies based on metadata and their possible extension, as well as meta-methodological issues about possible user scenarios of such ontologies within the historical network research community. The second research stream concerns the development of methods to extend the available network tools and approaches applicable to historical questions. The ModelSEN group is working on the integration of numerical, topological and agent-based methods, while others are developing statistical approaches for longitudinal multi-layer network analysis (Baccini and Petrovich 2017).

4. Current Common Research Goals and Questions

Regardless of the specifics of the different research projects, the group is united by the ambition to produce novel concepts and approaches that further develop the range of uses of network analysis in historical research. Irrespective of the variety of approaches in the realm of algorithmic analysis and visual representation of networks, we see a need to further extend, develop and improve network-based methodologies to address historical questions concerning social and epistemic processes. Therefore, we propose to establish a framework for the standardization of the procedures that will make these approaches more shareable and amenable to testing and, in the process, increases the robustness of observations and transferability of insights.

No single research question can capture the depth of our common goals, but during our workshop some prominent examples of overarching historical research objectives became apparent, mostly related to the history of science because of the focus of the ModelSEN project.

Some of these are more structural or methodological:

- How can we use network research to analyze processes of knowledge production, transfer, certification and stabilization? How are these processes related to the processes of (network-)growth and (network-)disintegration?

- How can we create a map of a research (sub-)field by considering producers of science, artifacts of science and concepts at the same time? How does this map change over time? Is it possible to represent and characterize these changes using network analysis?

Another set of questions is historical and regards the emergence and diffusion of innovation, or the formation of consensus (regarding fields, ideas, concepts or methods):

- Why do certain ideas, epistemic objects³ (e.g., models and theories), practices and people prevail? Why do some ideas, epistemic objects, and practices diffuse and others do not?
- What are the (social) conditions under which ideas, practices, or epistemic objects emerge and diffuse?
- How do research institutions, conferences, social gatherings, journals' editorial boards, etc. affect the diffusion of and the engagement with scientific ideas, epistemic objects, and practices?
- Why are some scholarly networks so resilient?

5. Future-looking Long-term Goals of this Group

At the current state the group has decided on two primary long-term goals.

Firstly, a long-term goal is to define and develop a set of (social) network analysis tools that are robust enough to be used for historical reconstructions or interpretations. This means testing whether tools already developed and established in other fields like SNA are sound when applied to historical questions. The aim is not to reinvent already existing solutions, but rather to reinterpret results and fields of application.

Secondly, the group has the goal of collectively defining best practices for the cleaning, modeling, storing and analyzing of historical data, as well as for the assessment of data reliability and completeness to allow for a meaningful network analysis (see desiderata below). This way, we hope to increase the reconciliation and comparability between datasets and the possibility to share and check each other's results.

Concrete steps to reach these goals already defined are:

- Develop an ontology for the description of networks that can be used in a variety of different projects (see below).
- Develop and test in different case studies a robust approach to deal with longitudinal multi-layer networks (see desiderata below).

³See e.g. Rheinberger, H-J. (1997). *Toward a History of Epistemic Things: Synthesizing Proteins in the Test Tube*. Stanford UP.

- Develop a workflow that allows to share and apply data, approaches and tools developed in one project to other projects.
- Create a more robust philosophical and theoretical assessment of what networks and their elements represent in historical perspectives.

6. Desiderata of Methods

New methods still have to be developed as part of the community process. As the outcome of the workshop, the following challenges need to be addressed with high priority:

With respect to data quality and data management:

- Dealing with dirty data (e.g., the problem of disambiguation of names and places) and negotiating fuzzy data (e.g., uncertain dating of events, absolute vs. relative order of events, contested information about objects and events, dealing with likelihoods and certainty of information).
- Data quality and errors: Based on statistical, historical and qualitative considerations, needed are methods for quantitatively and qualitatively describing errors as part of historical analysis, aiming towards a historical theory of errors in analogy to well-established methods of error propagation and error handling in the sciences.
- Missing and used data: Needed are stable methods for describing the provenience and the quality of data used, but also the coverage of the used data with respect to the historical question.
- Data mining: Needed are tools for extracting data from archival material.

With respect to the adequate algorithmic analysis of the structure and dynamics of networks and the underlying data:

- Time-dependent (multi-layer) networks: Needed are methods to deal with the speed of change in different layers, with changes on different time scales in the different layers, with the resilience of layers with respect to sudden changes of the environment or structural changes of one of the layers;
- Signed networks (e.g., the connection between opinion networks and friendship networks),
- Comparability of networks: Comparing the topology and temporality of networks.

7. Help Building the Community!

Researchers who work in the field of (historical) network research and are interested in partaking in the process of further community building are welcome to connect with the ModelSEN project.

7.1. Survey: Best-Practices and Tools in Historical Network Research

Addressing scholars working on the analysis of historical networks, this survey asks about views on common tools, practices and challenges with the explicit goal to inform the development of future research software and educational resources. Please, share your opinions and experiences in this survey! Follow this link to the survey: <https://survey.academiccloud.de/index.php/513751?lang=en>.

7.2. Building a Shared Ontology

The current state of the ontology is published and accessible in WebProtégé⁴. With this first draft of nodes, edges and networks, we invite the HNR community to collaboratively develop an ontology for the description of networks that can be used in a variety of different projects. Please, feel free to leave comments and share your ideas!

We intend to improve the ontology continuously from now on and invite interested parties for comments and cooperation⁵.

7.3. Establishment of the Compendium

The Compendium⁶ is a collection point of best-practice examples, tutorials and tools or source descriptions. This Compendium is edited by the ModelSEN group and we invite everyone to contribute by sending proposals for such publications.

For updates on the above-mentioned projects, please visit the ModelSEN website⁷.

⁴<https://webprotege.stanford.edu/#projects/e53f9f4c-da6e-49dd-9154-d25aba1db501> (sign in required).

⁵One proposed test-case for this ontology could be the modeling of “scientific observations” which is a common theme in the above-mentioned two historical research groups.

⁶Available at: <https://modelsen.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/compendium>.

⁷<https://modelsen.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/de/workshops/community/>

8. Next Steps

The group is intending to meet on a regular basis to sharpen the goals and methodologies. Members of the group are already involved in maintaining and organizing different modes of communication and publication within the community. The group aims at developing further these already existing channels to foster an active network of cooperation.

8.1. Next Workshop

In a second workshop organized by the ModelSEN project the community will focus on working on specific topics in smaller working groups to further sharpen the goals of the community and the methods.

8.2. HNR-Conferences

As soon as ontology and compendium have reached a level of maturity to be introduced into and used by the HNR community, workshops will take place in the context of the HNR conference. Several types of events are possible, e.g., data-thons where researchers work on describing their network data in an open collaborative space assisted by the ModelSEN group; workshops focusing on specific methods and their practical application; or thematically oriented sessions exploring one or more of the research fields discussed by the group.

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